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**Insilico docking studies on Afzellan and Jugalin as potential candidate for anti SARS
COV2 drug**

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The COVID 19 pandemic can be righteously said as the most infectious disease of the 21st century aided by the lack of proper antiviral medication. This has led for the need to develop a quick and efficient antiviral drug that can control this infectious disease. Kaempferol derivatives mainly “Afzellan” and “Jugallin” was studied for their antiviral properties. In this study, Kaempferol derivatives Afzellan and Jugalin were docked against spike protein of all variants and importantly against the spike protein of the infectious alpha and delta strain to identify novel target inhibitors. Compounds such as Afzellan, Astragalgin, and Kaempferol 3 alpha L Arabinoside have been found to bind to specific RBD sites in the delta strain. In alpha strain, the 3' kaempferol compounds, Afzellan and Jugalin, exhibited precise binding at par with Remdesivir medicine, causing them to display characteristics identical to the control medication. As a consequence, the selected kaempferol compounds bind to various binding sites of SARS Cov-2 variants and prevent spike glycoprotein from adhering to the ACE-2 human cell receptor, potentially limiting infectivity. So according to our molecular docking studies, several of the Kaempferol derivatives show binding affinity to numerous locations of the virus, including the RBD domain, that is comparable to that of known anti-viral medicines like Remdesivir and Favipiravir.

According to our in-silico research, these compounds have a lot of potential as anti-COVID-19 medications. However, because most current research is focused on molecular stimulation, more in-vitro and in-vivo testing is necessary. As a consequence, with further modification and validation, including preclinical and clinical research, these compounds can be considered as potential inhibitors and antiviral medications for human use.